

Short communication

First record of *Cladius (Priophorus) rufipes* (Hym.: Tenthredinidae) from Iran

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چکیده

در بررسی آفات درختان نارون در شهر رشت، در اواسط اردیبهشت ۱۳۹۰، لاروهای زنبور مشاهده و جمع‌آوری شد. جهت دست‌یابی به حشرات کامل، لاروهای آفت در آزمایشگاه پرورش داده شدند. این زنبور توسط نگارنده آخر با نام علمی *Cladius (Priophorus) rufipes* Serville مورد شناسایی قرار گرفت. گونه مذکور گزارش جدیدی برای فون ایران محسوب می‌شود.

Cladius rufipes Serville, which belongs to Cladiini of Nematinae, was first described from France. Subsequently it has been associated with the genus-group names *Cladius* Illiger, *Priophorus* Dahlbom and *Trichiocampus* Hartig (see Taeger *et al.* (2010) for various combinations). Literature data on the ecology and distribution of *C. rufipes* are sometimes ambiguous to interpret, because for a long time the name *ulmi* Linné, has been applied for *rufipes* (e.g. Konow, 1897; Zhelochovtsev, 1952). According to Benson (1961), the name *Cladius ulmi* (Linné) is to be referred to a *Cladius (Trichiocampus)* species, whose larvae are associated with elm as the host plant as well as those of *C. rufipes* (= *ulmi* auct.). Therefore, records from the literature may be confusing (Chevin, 1997).

Comparatively few publications consider the sawfly fauna of Iran. The latest comprehensive study is that of Benson (1968) on the sawflies of Turkey, which also includes numerous records for Iran, and also records *C. rufipes* for Turkey. Some additional works in the fields of ecology and applied entomology consider sawfly species, which occur as pests of crops and ornamental plants in Iran (e.g. Davoudi, 1987, 1995; Ghadiri, 1994; Ghadiri & Safai, 2001; Sahragard & Heydari, 2001), but none of these has mentioned anything about the occurrence of *C. rufipes* in the country, and therefore here it is recorded for the first time from Iran.

- *Cladius (Priophorus) rufipes* Serville

Material examined – Guilan province, Rasht: 5.v.2011, leg. Roya Khosravi, ex: *Ulmus glabra*. 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂ in the collection of the Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut and 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂ in the collection of Department of Plant Protection, University of Guilan.

Diagnosis – Contrary to other *Cladius* species, *C. rufipes* is characterized by the combination of black body, orange femora, tibiae and tarsi; presence of a large basal, ventral process on flagellomere I (Zhelochovtsev, 1952, fig. 1.4) and absence of dorsal rami on several flagellomeres of the male. The penis valve of the male specimens from Iran corresponds with the illustration given by Zhelochovtsev (1952, fig. 3.2).

Hosts – Literature data for the larval host plants include wych elm (*Ulmus glabra* Huds.) (Pschorn-Walcher & Altenhofer, 2006), European white elm (*U. laevis* Pallas) (Liston, 2007), and field elm (*U. minor* Mill. var. *vulgaris* (Aiton) R. H. Richens), which was treated by Halstead (2001) as a separate species, *U. procera* Salisb.

Distribution – The distribution of *C. rufipes* extends in Europe from southern Scandinavia (Kakko, 2009) to Italy and the Balkans, and from Great Britain to Russia (Taeger *et al.*, 2006). Benson (1968) listed *Priophorus rufipes* (Serville) for the Asian part of Turkey and for Trans-Caucasus. According to Zhelochovtsev &

Zinovjev (1995), records from the Ukraine and Caucasus are doubtful. Also, Lacourt's (1999) mention of Central Asia appears very ambiguous, because Mucbe's (1976) record of *Trichiocampus ulmi* (L.)

from Tadjikistan seems to refer actually to the species currently called *Cladius (Trichiocampus) ulmi* (L.) (see Mucbe, 1975).

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